

Conversational Implicature in Contemporary Religious Discourse: A Comparative Pragmatic Study of Muhammad Husayn Tabataba'i and Mohammad Mohammad Sadeq al-Sadr

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Abstract

This study investigates conversational implicature in contemporary religious discourse through a comparative pragmatic analysis of two prominent Islamic thinkers: Muhammad Husayn Tabataba'i and Mohammad Mohammad Sadeq al-Sadr. Grounded in Paul Grice's theory of conversational implicature and the Cooperative Principle, the research explores how meaning extends beyond literal expression through intentional or context-driven violations of conversational maxims.

The study adopts a comparative analytical methodology, examining selected textual examples from Qur'anic exegesis and religious-political discourse. It demonstrates that al-Tabataba'i employs conversational implicature primarily as an interpretive tool within a philosophical and exegetical framework, where implicatures arise from textual structure and contextual reading of the Qur'an. In contrast, al-Sadr utilizes implicature as a persuasive and directive communicative strategy aimed at influencing audiences within socio-political and religious contexts.

Findings reveal that violations of Gricean maxims (Quantity, Quality, Relation, and Manner) function not as communicative failures but as deliberate pragmatic strategies for generating implicit meaning. The study concludes that conversational implicature plays a crucial role in constructing meaning in religious discourse and highlights the importance of pragmatic approaches in bridging linguistic theory with Islamic intellectual traditions.

Keywords: *Conversational implicature, Pragmatics, Grice, Religious discourse, al-Tabataba'i, al-Sadr, Cooperative Principle.*

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Introduction

Contemporary linguistic studies have witnessed a significant shift in their conception of language. Language is no longer regarded as a closed formal system limited to structure and syntax; rather, it is increasingly viewed as a communicative practice closely linked to context, speaker intention, and the relationship between discourse and its audience. Within this framework, pragmatics has emerged as a prominent field of inquiry concerned with uncovering meanings that are not explicitly stated but are inferred through context, situational requirements, principles of conversational cooperation, and the implicatures generated thereby.

Conversational implicature is considered one of the most influential concepts in pragmatics, particularly following the formulation of the theory of conversational cooperation by the philosopher of language Paul Grice. Grice proposed the Cooperative Principle and its four conversational maxims—Quantity, Quality, Relation, and Manner—which provide a framework for understanding how interlocutors move from literal meaning to implied meaning. This approach offers a more precise explanation of how speakers intentionally violate certain conversational norms in order to convey indirect meanings that hearers infer through contextual reasoning.

Although the theory of conversational implicature originated within Western linguistic scholarship, its application to the analysis of Arabic-Islamic religious, exegetical, and intellectual discourse remains highly promising. Religious discourse fundamentally relies on interaction between text and audience, guiding interpretation beyond the apparent meaning of words toward broader objectives of guidance, instruction, moral cultivation, and the formation of consciousness. Consequently, there is a need for a pragmatic approach capable of revealing the implicature-based dimensions of such discourse and demonstrating how conversational principles—whether observed or intentionally violated—contribute to meaning construction.

Within this context, the present study examines the pragmatic dimension of the discourse of two prominent contemporary Islamic thinkers: Muhammad Husayn Tabataba'i and Mohammad Mohammad Sadeq al-Sadr. Through the lens of conversational implicature, the study seeks to uncover the mechanisms through which this pragmatic phenomenon operates in their texts and to identify similarities and differences in their respective approaches to generating meaning through the intentional violation of conversational maxims.

This comparison is significant for several reasons. First, al-Tabataba'i is widely recognized as one of the foremost representatives of philosophical and analytical Qur'anic exegesis in the twentieth century. His exegetical discourse is characterized by rigorous reasoning, contextual analysis of Qur'anic passages, and the integration of individual meanings into the broader textual system. Such features create ample opportunities for the deployment of conversational implicature, particularly through deliberate elaboration, rhetorical questioning, and the expansion of meaning by means of violating the maxims of Quantity and Relation.

In contrast, al-Sadr represents a model of dynamic socio-religious discourse directed toward a broad public audience and shaped by complex political, security, and cultural circumstances. Consequently, his discourse relies heavily on suggestion, implication, intensification, and deliberate prolixity as pragmatic strategies for generating meanings that extend beyond explicit expression.

Second, the comparison between these two figures extends beyond the distinction between exegetical and public discourse to encompass differences in pragmatic orientation itself. Al-Tabataba'i tends to construct conversational implicature within a calm textual-analytical framework grounded in the structure and context of Qur'anic discourse. Al-Sadr, on the other hand, employs conversational implicature as a persuasive and directive communicative tool closely connected to social and political realities, as well as to the audience's knowledge, experience, and expectations.

Third, the study seeks to address a relative gap in Arabic pragmatic scholarship. Existing studies have often approached conversational implicature from either a theoretical perspective or through limited

applications, without conducting in-depth comparative analyses between thinkers who belong to the same intellectual tradition, share a common religious reference framework, yet differ in the nature and function of their discourse. Accordingly, this study aims to contribute to the enrichment of pragmatic research and to strengthen its connection with contemporary Qur'anic and intellectual studies.

Based on these considerations, the present article aims to:

1. Clarify the theoretical foundations of conversational implicature and its pragmatic principles.
2. Identify manifestations of conversational maxim violations in the discourse of al-Tabataba'i and al-Sadr.
3. Conduct a comparative analytical examination of the two thinkers' approaches to employing conversational implicature.
4. Highlight the pragmatic and functional dimensions through which conversational implicature contributes to the production of religious and intellectual meaning.

The study adopts a comparative pragmatic-analytical methodology. It begins with a presentation of the theoretical framework and proceeds to the analysis of selected textual examples, ultimately deriving semantic and implicatural conclusions while taking into account the intellectual and social contexts of each thinker. Furthermore, it seeks to integrate insights from modern linguistic theory with traditional exegetical and rhetorical scholarship, thereby establishing a methodological synthesis between linguistic inquiry and religious thought.

Conversational Implicature

Conversational implicature is one of the most prominent concepts upon which modern pragmatic linguistics is grounded. It represents a turning point in understanding meaning in human communication, as it is considered an inherent phenomenon of natural language and a fundamental feature of its semantic and pragmatic dimensions. This concept is inseparable from the act of communication itself, as every linguistic interaction is based on two layers: an explicit meaning conveyed through the syntactic structure of the sentence, and an implicit meaning inferred from the speaker's intentions and contextual circumstances, which is known as conversational implicature.

Grice's efforts opened new horizons in pragmatic studies when he introduced the Cooperative Principle and its accompanying maxims that govern conversational behavior and enable interlocutors to infer implied meanings beyond utterances. Grice's central idea was that linguistic utterances do not merely convey literal meaning, and that speakers often say one thing while meaning another, and listeners hear one thing while understanding something different. This theoretical foundation was later developed as "implicit communication," since speakers shape their discourse in ways that generate additional meanings not explicitly stated.

Accordingly, conversational implicature has been defined as: "something the speaker determines, suggests, and implies, which is not part of the literal meaning of the sentence" (Salih, 2007, p. 78). This definition shows that implicature is neither a spoken meaning nor a fixed syntactic meaning, but rather an inferred meaning based on the listener's recognition of the speaker's intention and the relationship between text and context.

Grice's primary objective in proposing the Cooperative Principle was to address the following problem: How can a speaker say one thing but intend another meaning? And how can the listener understand this unspoken meaning? To answer these questions, Grice proposed a set of conversational maxims that regulate human dialogue and allow interlocutors to correctly interpret intended meanings through what he called "conversational implicature," a semantic shift from explicit to implicit meaning governed by contextual conditions.

This concept is based on the idea that when a speaker intentionally violates one of the conversational maxims, the violation is not random, but rather serves to communicate an additional hidden meaning.

Pragmatists refer to this process as the transition from literal meaning to implied meaning, a process that depends on the listener's inferential abilities and awareness of contextual and communicative intentions.

Based on this understanding, scholars have distinguished between explicit and implicit meaning, arguing that “the semantic content of a linguistic expression can be divided into two types: explicit meanings and implicit meanings” (Al-Ayashi, 2011, p. 15). The first type is directly expressed by the sentence structure, while the second emerges from context and communicative intention. Thus, a speaker may use an utterance without intending its literal meaning, instead employing it to convey an alternative meaning, which results in the semantic shift at the heart of conversational implicature.

Because this concept is inherently context-dependent, scholars have regarded it as a bridge between literal meaning and pragmatic meaning determined by situational factors. Therefore, conversational implicature has become a central tool in discourse analysis, particularly in religious, literary, and argumentative texts, which contain multiple layers of meaning beyond the surface level.

The Emergence of Conversational Implicature and Its Major Scholars

Conversational implicature theory is one of the most significant contributions of 20th-century pragmatic linguistics. Its emergence is closely associated with the philosopher Paul Grice, who is considered the true founder of this concept. His interest in communicative mechanisms and their problems arose within the context of analytic philosophy, which focused on language use rather than structure alone.

The starting point was his influential 1957 paper entitled *Meaning*, which had a profound impact on pragmatics by highlighting the role of inference in communication and the cognitive processes involved in moving from utterance to intended meaning. This work demonstrated that linguistic communication relies not only on explicit meaning but also on contextual and rational cues (see Abdul Rahman, 2012, pp. 235–236).

Grice further developed his ideas in his famous 1975 article “Logic and Conversation,” where he established the theoretical foundations of what later became known as conversational implicature. He distinguished between natural and non-natural meaning and explored how discourse is produced and interpreted beyond linguistic convention, relying instead on intention and context. In this work, he introduced two key concepts: conversational implicature and the Cooperative Principle, which became central to modern pragmatics (see Anne Reboul, 2003, p. 54).

For Grice, conversational implicature is based on the distinction between what is said and what is implicated. The propositional content corresponds to the literal meaning of the utterance, whereas implicature refers to what is inferred beyond the literal statement. This meaning is non-truth-conditional, as it depends on the listener's interpretation of the hidden meaning rather than the propositional truth of the utterance (see Moeschler & Reboul, 2010, pp. 265–266).

An example provided by Grice illustrates this distinction:

1. It is true that Zayd is a linguist.
2. It is surprising that Zayd is a linguist.

The first sentence is true only if the proposition “Zayd is a linguist” is true, whereas the second expresses surprise regardless of the truth value of the proposition itself.

The Cooperative Principle forms the foundation of Grice's theory. It assumes that participants in conversation share a common communicative goal that leads them to implicitly follow conversational rules. These rules are not grammatical laws but pragmatic assumptions that enable interpretation. Without such cooperation, communication becomes ambiguous or fails entirely (see Philippe, 2007, p. 84).

Following Grice and Searle, many scholars contributed to the development of implicature theory, including Erving Goffman, John Gumperz, Teun van Dijk, Bateson, Habermas, Watzlawick, and others. Their contributions expanded the theory into legal, political, educational, and sociolinguistic domains.

The Roots of Conversational Implicature in the Classical Arabic Linguistic Tradition

Conversational implicature is not a purely modern invention; rather, it extends from long-standing intellectual traditions in Arabic linguistics concerning the relationship between utterance and implied meaning, and the contextual orientation of discourse.

Classical Arab linguists and critics expressed this phenomenon through various conceptual and methodological frameworks that can be interpreted as early or foundational approximations of what is now known as conversational implicature.

Fakhr al-Din al-Razi observed that “when a word is assigned to a referent, the mind moves from that referent to its implication,” indicating a cognitive transition from explicit expression to implied meaning. This closely aligns with Grice’s notion of implicature, where meaning extends beyond literal expression.

‘Abd al-Qahir al-Jurjani introduced the concept of “meaning of meaning” (ma‘nā al-ma‘nā), distinguishing between surface meaning produced by linguistic form and deeper meaning derived from it. This distinction closely parallels the modern transition from literal to implied meaning.

Ibn Jinni and other linguists emphasized intention as central to language, viewing linguistic expression as a reflection of speaker intention beyond lexical meaning. This aligns with pragmatic approaches to discourse analysis.

Al-Sakkaki, in *Miftab al-‘Ulum*, explicitly linked syntactic structure with contextual necessity, emphasizing that “every context has its own appropriate expression.” This highlights the importance of situational factors in interpreting meaning.

Rhetorical devices such as metaphor, irony, allusion, and ellipsis function as mechanisms for generating implied meanings, requiring the listener to actively infer unstated meanings.

Ibn Khaldun also contributed by analyzing social and psychological dimensions of communication, helping explain why speakers often imply more than they explicitly state.

In conclusion, the Arabic linguistic heritage provides a rich conceptual foundation for conversational implicature, offering early theoretical insights into intention, context, and inferred meaning.

Al-Tabataba’i

Muhammad Husayn al-Tabataba’i (1904–1981) is a distinguished Shiite scholar whose lineage traces back to Imam Hasan ibn Ali on his father’s side and Imam Husayn ibn Ali on his mother’s side (Husayni al-Tehrani, 1433 AH, pp. 33–34). He is known by titles such as al-Hasani, al-Husayni, and al-Tabataba’i (al-Ausi, 1985, p. 36).

He was born on March 17, 1904, in Tabriz, Iran, into a scholarly and cultured family. His lineage is connected to Mir Abd al-Wahhab, who served as Shaykh al-Islam in Azerbaijan during the Safavid era (al-Amin, 1403 AH, p. 254).

He studied under prominent scholars, including Mirza Ali Qadi, and attained ijthihad and scholarly authorization from major authorities such as al-Naini (al-Rifa’i, 2001, p. 93).

He later migrated to Najaf in 1344 AH, where he studied jurisprudence and philosophy under leading scholars, including Shaykh Muhammad Husayn al-Isfahani and Ayatollah Abu al-Hasan al-Isfahani (al-Haydari, 2007, p. 7).

He studied philosophy under Sayyid Husayn Badkubi, engaging with major philosophical works such as *Al-Asfar*, *Al-Shifa*, and others, alongside mathematics and logic training.

His major works include:

1. *Al-Mizan fi Tafsir al-Qur’an* (20 volumes), translated into Persian and English.

2. *Bidayat al-Hikmah*
3. *Nibayat al-Hikmah*
4. Commentary on *Al-Asfar*
5. Dialogues with Henry Corbin
6. *Risalat al-Hukuma al-Islamiyya*
7. *Risalat al-Qumwa wa al-Fi'l*
8. *Risalat al-Mughallata*
9. *Ali and Divine Philosophy*

Al-Tabataba'i is widely regarded as one of the most influential exegetes of the 20th century, particularly for his philosophical and analytical approach to Qur'anic interpretation.

Al-Sadr

Sayyid Muhammad Muhammad Sadiq al-Sadr (1943–1999) belongs to a noble lineage tracing back to Imam Musa al-Kazim (al-Sadr, 2019, p. 45).

He was born on March 23, 1943, in Najaf al-Ashraf (al-Sadr, 1431 AH, p. 10). He grew up in a distinguished scholarly family known for piety and learning, including prominent figures such as Shaykh Muhammad Rida al-Yasin and his father Sayyid Muhammad Sadiq al-Sadr (d. 1403 AH).

After the death of Grand Ayatollah Abu al-Qasim al-Khoei, he emerged as a leading religious authority in 1993. He played a significant role in revitalizing the seminary of Najaf, supporting students, promoting religious education, and engaging with society's needs, particularly among disadvantaged groups.

His major works include:

1. *Ma Wara' al-Fiqh* (10-volume jurisprudential encyclopedia)
2. *Fiqh al-Akblaq*
3. *Mawsu'at al-Imam al-Mahdi* (4 volumes)
4. *Islamic Perspectives on Human Rights*
5. *Asbi'a min 'Aqa'id al-Islam*
6. *Manhaj al-Salihin*
7. *Fiqh al-Fada'*
8. *Minat al-Mannan fi al-Difa' 'an al-Qur'an* (5 volumes)
9. *Lights on the Revolution of Imam Husayn (peace be upon him)*

He authored numerous additional works in jurisprudence, theology, and social thought.

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Principles of Conversational Implicature

Conversational implicature is considered one of the most important pragmatic foundations in modern linguistic studies. It is based on the central idea that linguistic communication cannot be successfully achieved unless interlocutors adhere to a set of principles and regulative constraints that organize discourse and guide participants toward constructing and exchanging meaning in a clear and effective

manner. From this perspective, conversation between two individuals is not merely an exchange of sentences, but rather a social act governed by communicative rules that form an essential part of pragmatic theory.

This approach is grounded in the work of Paul Grice and his well-known theory of discourse rules or conversational maxims. These principles regulate all natural conversation and are an extension of his general principle known as the Cooperative Principle. This principle assumes that when speakers engage in linguistic interaction, they expect one another to contribute in ways that make communication possible and to perform their roles according to implicit rules that are understood by competent language users.

Accordingly, communication can only proceed successfully when it is based on this general principle, since any deviation from it leads to disruption in conversational flow and semantic breakdown that hinders understanding. Several scholars have emphasized this point, noting that the relationship between interlocutors can only be understood through these social and interactional constraints that govern discourse structure and its nature (see: Saber, 2008, p. 20).

Building on this principle, Grice proposed four fundamental maxims that constitute the core of his theory of conversational implicature, which determine the nature of conversational contribution (see: Bahaa al-Din, 2010, p. 40):

1. Maxim of Quantity

This maxim requires the speaker to provide the appropriate amount of information—neither more than required, which may confuse the listener, nor less than required, which may lead to incomplete understanding. It concerns the quantity of information rather than its relevance or truthfulness.

2. Maxim of Quality

This maxim requires the speaker to be truthful and not provide information known to be false or unsupported by evidence. Quality here is related to the sincerity and verifiability of the utterance.

3. Maxim of Relation (Relevance)

This maxim requires that the speaker's contribution be relevant to the topic of conversation, without deviation. Since every situation has its appropriate discourse, deviation from relevance disrupts communication and obscures meaning.

4. Maxim of Manner

This maxim requires clarity of expression, avoiding ambiguity, obscurity, unnecessary prolixity, or excessive brevity, while maintaining an orderly linguistic structure appropriate to the interlocutors' level and background.

Together, these maxims form the foundation upon which conversational implicature is built. Any violation of them does not necessarily indicate communicative failure; rather, it may be intentional and aimed at generating additional implicit meaning that the hearer must infer from the context of the violation. Thus, these principles function as a guiding framework for understanding the relationship between literal and implied meaning.

Several later scholars sought to develop Grice's theory due to its significant analytical potential. For instance, Henrich merged some maxims such as quantity and quality, while Sadok reduced and modified them and introduced additional criteria. Wilson and Sperber, however, critically challenged Grice's maxims, arguing that they are insufficient for analyzing literary and legal texts characterized by deep and multi-layered contextual structures. They proposed an alternative theory, Relevance Theory, which later became a widely influential cognitive framework in modern linguistic analysis (see: Mahmoud, 2013, pp. 94–95).

Thus, Grice's theory represents a fundamental starting point for studying conversational implicature, while subsequent developments expanded its scope to include diverse forms of discourse, revealing that

successful communication depends on shared intentions and adherence to the rules governing meaning production and interpretation.

Conventional Conversational Implicature (Exploitation)

A speaker may sometimes deliberately violate conversational maxims in an overt manner in order to generate intentional conversational implicature. In such cases, the speaker intends the addressee to recognize that the violation is deliberate and that the breach of cooperative principles is what generates the implied meaning, while still remaining within the framework of the Cooperative Principle. This requires that the speaker be careful to convey a specific intended meaning, while the hearer actively works to infer it. When a maxim is violated, the hearer attempts to uncover the speaker's intended meaning behind this violation (see: Mahmoud, 2002, pp. 35–36).

A speaker may also violate one maxim in order to preserve another; for example, the maxim of quantity may be breached by withholding information in order to preserve the maxim of quality by remaining truthful. This leads the hearer to infer an implicature such as the speaker's lack of full knowledge of the requested information (see: Hafez, 2014, pp. 164–165).

The purposes of such violations cannot be restricted to rhetorical figures alone. Not all violations produce stylistic or figurative effects; rather, they may serve politeness strategies, evasion of responsibility, brevity, intensification, or symbolic expression (see: Muhammad, 2018, p. 117).

In the following, we examine examples of maxim violation in the writings of Muhammad Husayn al-Tabataba'i and Muhammad Muhammad Sadiq al-Sadr.

First: Violation of the Maxim of Quantity

The maxim of quantity requires a balance between expression and meaning, ensuring that speech corresponds to the intended meaning without excess or deficiency (see: al-Ayyashi, 2011, p. 99). Excess or omission may lead the hearer to infer an intentional purpose behind the deviation.

Al-Tabataba'i's interpretation of the Qur'anic verse:

"And what is that in your right hand, O Moses?"

He said:

"It is my staff; I lean on it, and I use it to bring down leaves for my sheep, and I have other uses for it." (Tabataba'i 20:17–18)

demonstrates this principle. The question posed is not intended to elicit unknown information, but rather to prompt elaboration. Moses' answer exceeds the required information, thus constituting a violation of quantity. The response could have been limited to "It is my staff," but he expanded it by mentioning its functions, reflecting the context of intimate divine communication.

From this, an implicature arises: the prolongation of the answer indicates a state of spiritual intimacy and engagement in divine dialogue, rather than informational necessity.

Similarly, Muhammad Muhammad Sadiq al-Sadr employs quantity violation through excessive enumeration and elaboration to produce implicit meanings beyond the literal statement, often to emphasize discipline, warning, or ideological orientation.

Second: Violation of the Maxim of Quality

The maxim of quality requires speakers to present only what they believe to be true and to avoid false or unsupported statements. In pragmatic theory, "lying" is not treated purely as a moral category but as a linguistic one related to mismatch between utterance and reality (see: Robrond, 1998, p. 496).

Under this maxim, al-Tabataba'i analyzes the statement:

"If he steals, a brother of his has stolen before him" (Yusuf 12:77)

as a violation of truthfulness by Joseph's brothers, revealing jealousy and psychological tension. The utterance is false in its apparent content but reveals an underlying implicature of self-exoneration and hidden resentment.

In al-Sadr's discourse, violations of quality appear in metaphorical, sarcastic, or rhetorical forms rather than literal falsehood, producing implicatures related to critique, warning, or moral condemnation.

Third: Violation of the Maxim of Manner

The maxim of manner requires clarity, organization, and avoidance of ambiguity. Violations occur when speech becomes vague, disordered, or deliberately indirect.

In the Qur'anic verse:

"Is this the one who insults your gods?" (Al-Anbiya 21:36)

al-Tabataba'i explains that the expression employs rhetorical ambiguity and sarcasm rather than literal questioning. The implicature reveals contempt and mockery rather than inquiry.

Similarly, al-Sadr uses deliberate ambiguity and generalization, particularly in politically sensitive contexts, where indirectness serves both protective and persuasive functions.

Fourth: Violation of the Maxim of Relation (Relevance)

The maxim of relation requires discourse to remain relevant to the topic. Deviations from relevance may generate strong implicatures.

Al-Tabataba'i interprets Satan's response:

"I am better than him" (Al-A'raf 7:12)

as irrelevant to the question "What prevented you from prostrating?", thereby generating the implicature of arrogance and self-exaltation.

Al-Sadr, on the other hand, uses irrelevance strategically to shock the audience and redirect attention toward implicit meanings, transforming deviation into a rhetorical device.

Comparative Analysis of al-Tabataba'i and al-Sadr in Conversational Implicature

The comparative pragmatic study of al-Tabataba'i and al-Sadr reveals clear differences in their use of conversational implicature, arising from differences in intellectual context and communicative function.

Al-Tabataba'i employs implicature as an interpretive analytical tool aimed at uncovering hidden Qur'anic meanings within linguistic and contextual frameworks. Violations of maxims in his analysis are not attributed to human speakers but are interpreted as deliberate rhetorical structures within the sacred text.

In contrast, al-Sadr employs implicature as a direct communicative and argumentative strategy aimed at influencing, mobilizing, or warning the audience within real socio-political contexts. His violations of maxims are intentional rhetorical acts designed to produce ideological and emotional effects.

Quantity

For al-Tabataba'i, quantity violation functions as interpretive expansion within the Qur'anic text. For al-Sadr, it functions as rhetorical amplification for mobilization and warning.

Quality

For al-Tabataba'i, it reveals contradictions and moral deviation. For al-Sadr, it operates through metaphor, irony, and rhetorical exaggeration.

Manner

For al-Tabataba'i, it is a textual feature analyzed for meaning. For al-Sadr, it is a protective and strategic indirectness.

Relation

For al-Tabataba'i, irrelevance reveals psychological and doctrinal deviation. For al-Sadr, it is a deliberate shock strategy.

Conclusion

The study concludes that conversational implicature constitutes a central mechanism in the construction of meaning in religious discourse, and that violations of Grice's Cooperative Principles should not be understood as communicative failures, but rather as pragmatic strategies for producing deeper implicit meanings aligned with contextual requirements.

Al-Tabataba'i employs implicature as an interpretive tool for Qur'anic exegesis, while al-Sadr employs it as a communicative strategy for persuasion, guidance, and socio-political engagement. Despite sharing a religious reference framework, their pragmatic functions diverge according to context.

This confirms that pragmatic analysis, particularly conversational implicature, provides an effective approach to understanding religious discourse and the relationship between language, meaning, and context.

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